

THE ADVANTAGES OF RESTRICTED MEAN SURVIVAL TIME IN ANALYSING KAPLAN-MEIER SURVIVAL CURVES: ANALYSIS OF 55 ARTICLES PUBLISHED IN THE LAST 12 MONTHS

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The literature on the restricted mean survival time (RMST) has grown markedly in the last months. We carried out a literature search on PubMed (date of the search: 5 July 2020; keyword: “restricted mean survival time”; filter: last 12 months) to quantify the growth of this literature over the past 12 months.

Our search identified a total of 62 papers. We examined these 62 papers individually and we found that, in 55 cases, the RMST could be considered an important methodological feature of the article. Despite the subjective nature of this analysis, this search indicates that an extensive research is currently being focused on the RMST.

In 30 of these 55 articles [1-30], the RMST was an explicit methodological objective of the article. In the remaining 25 articles [31-55], the RMST was more simply a tool employed to conduct the clinical research.

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ADDENDUM OF 13 JULY 2020

In 2019 or 2020, each of the following 8 authoritative journals (New England Journal of Medicine, Lancet, Journal of Clinical Oncology, Annals of Internal Medicine, Annals of Oncology, JAMA Oncology, Circulation, and Journal of the National Comprehensive Cancer Network) have published at least one methodological paper that emphasized the advantages of the RMST in comparison with the HR [1-10]; in particular, the Journal of Clinical Oncology and the Annals of Internal Medicine have each published two such papers over this short time interval of less than two years [1,4,6,10].

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